

9

An Eco-critical Study of Adrienne Rich's Poems

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Abstract: *Eco-criticism is the study of literature and environment, where literary scholars analyse texts that illustrate environmental concerns. It focuses on ecological imbalance and is critical of anthropocentric perspectives, arguing in favor of an ecocentric approach to the natural environment.*

In light of the above definition, this paper attempts to situate Adrienne Rich's poem, "Trying to Talk to a Man", in which the ecological imbalance is prompted by the testing of nuclear bombs, and the environment is transformed into a desert. The environmental pollution and ecological imbalance have a negative impact on human psychology, and this is evident from the unhappy relationship between the husband and the wife in the poem. Likewise, in another poem, Diving into the Wreck, the woman, in order to get rid of her social limitations, escapes into nature to find freedom. Diving into the water gives her relief and peace. The eco-critics are of the view that both women and nature are exploited by the dominant, destructive force. Water, being one of the most important elements, is presented here as a lifesaver and the only reason behind human existence. It also shows how ecological preservation can benefit humans for a better livelihood. The connection between deep ecology and the oppression of women will be highlighted here. For the Record is another poem in which Rich shows how nature is innocent about the atrocities committed by humankind, even though the phenomenon of nature may cause natural calamities. Humans are responsible and guilty for the wars that bring about the destruction of the environment

and change the face of the earth. Pollution arising from wars leads to the dislocation of people and death due to starvation. Rich, through these poems, asks her readers to have a holistic view and respect towards our ecology.

Keywords: Nature, eco-criticism, ecology, environment.

Introduction

Eco-criticism is the study of literature and environment, where literary scholars analyze texts that illustrate environmental concerns. It focuses on ecological imbalance and is critical of anthropocentric perspectives, arguing in favor of an ecocentric approach to the natural environment. It is also known by other names such as “green (cultural) studies”, “ecopoetics”, and “environmental literary criticism”.

Ecocriticism, as a school of literary criticism, started in the 1990s as a meeting of American critics dealing with American literature that led the eco-critics to the foundation of ASLE (Association for the Study of Literature and Environment) and their Journal ISLE (Interdisciplinary Studies in Literature and Environment), and thereafter, with every next conference, it started gaining wide international recognition. It is also important to note that it is the initiative taken by the young people that stresses the longevity of this holistic and humanistic discipline. The most widely known eco-critics are Lawrence Buell, Cheryll Glotfelty, Simon C. Estok, Harold Fromm, William Howarth, William Rueckert, Suellen Campbell, Michael P. Branch, and Glen A. Love. (Tosic, 44)

Ecocriticism is the word which is recently been used in the published anthology, *The Ecocriticism Reader: Landmarks in Literary Ecology* (1996) edited by Cheryll Glotfelty and Harold Fromm. The book is a collection of essays with an ecological approach to literary studies, which indicates that the aim of ecocriticism is to transform literary studies by associating literary criticism and theories with ecological issues. Ecocriticism calls on

literature to connect to the issues of the environment and undertake a major step to redefine it. It is one of the ways in which humanists fight for a healthy world in which they live. Over-exploitation of natural resources and man's disregard of the air, water, and soil that sustain him have given rise to the question of his survival on planet Earth. The reflection of this speaks for the urgent need to do something in this serious matter.

Ecocriticism corresponds with the term 'ecology' as both have the same aim. Ecology and literary criticism, which belong to two separate disciplines, are combined in order to restore Earth's health lost by the careless behaviour of humans who dwell in it. Ecology is the science that studies the relationship between living organisms (biotic and abiotic) and the natural environment in which they live. Deep ecology is another term that originated from the endeavour to promote life and stresses the fact that man is a huge part of nature, and so he needs to realise that he is not allowed to reduce the richness and variety of the living world, but only use it for the satisfaction of his basic needs. It also emphasises the role of the individual to behave as a citizen of the world and earth to take responsibility. This deep ecology movement is gaining influence year by year, especially in America. This movement is holistic and acknowledges the unity of man and all the creatures and the environment around him. (Tosic, 45)

Discussion

Literature and particularly poetry have also served the purpose of highlighting the problems regarding the deterioration of the health of the environment around us and creating awareness for its preservation. In this regard, it would be profitable to situate the poems of Adrienne Rich from her selected Volumes titled *Diving into the Wreck* (1973) and *Your Native Land, Your Life* (1986).

Adrienne Rich, the twentieth-century American poet, has stressed the growing and widening gap between human beings and nature. Mostly known for her women-centered poems, her works also

envision nature-related problems, which are also a part of marginalization, as experienced by her female subjects. In this respect, Rich's poetry deals with issues of ecology to demonstrate the relationship among human subjectivity, cultural discourse, and nature. It is perhaps best to interpret Adrienne Rich's poems through an ecocritical point of view, as her poetry moves from radical feminism to ecofeminism.

In the poem "Trying to Talk to a Man" selected from the first volume, the speaker and her husband have travelled to a site in the desert where the American army is testing bombs:

Out in this desert we are testing bombs
that's why we came here. (1-2)

There is a lack of respect for the delicate desert ecosystem. The patriarchal power and arrogance threaten the world with the nuclear weapons being putatively tested in this landscape. The landscape mentioned is the Nevada Test Site region, which was earlier inhabited by the indigenous Paiute and Western Shoshone, who suffered most directly because of the effects of the patriarchal military and scientific complex inflicted on this particular landscape. The ecological imbalance is prompted by the testing of nuclear bombs, and the environment is transformed into a desert. It has been well said that forests precede mankind; deserts follow, and this is due to the atrocious behaviour of the human race. Fisheries, forests, grasslands, and croplands altogether form the foundation of the global economic system, but in many large areas of the world, human claims on these systems are reaching an unsustainable level, a point where their productivity is being impaired, like the desert mentioned in the poem. The environmental pollution and ecological imbalance caused by the testing of nuclear bombs have a negative impact on human psychology, and this is evident from the unhappy relationship between the husband and the wife in the poem. The speaker also expresses that she senses a river flowing beneath the dry and arid desert:

Sometimes I feel an underground river (3)

which advocate for a new possibility emerging into this “condemned scenery”, a sense of understanding that such sites sacrifice us all, beginning with the most vulnerable, already exploited populations. The poem is a clear indication of how humans exploit the environment in which they live, not realizing the aftermath of their inhuman actions.

In another poem of the same title, “Diving into the Wreck”, the woman, in order to get rid of her social limitations and oppressions of the patriarchal world, escapes into nature to find freedom. Metaphorically, the world in which she lives suffocates her, and as such, she searches for tranquility, which only nature could provide, and so diving into the water gives her relief and peace. The eco-critics are of the view that both women and nature are exploited by the dominant, destructive force. Water, being one of the most important elements, is presented here as a lifesaver and the only reason behind human existence. It also shows how ecological preservation can benefit humans for a better livelihood. As Nature represents women, the protagonist dives into her own nature, starts to explore herself, and feels more comfortable as she goes down into the sea. The persona came down to see the damage of the wreck:

the evidence of damage
worn by salt and sway into this threadbare beauty. (67-68)

The wreck caused by the sea indicates how powerful nature can be both as a destroyer and a saviour. She has suffered immensely under the dominance of the patriarchal world, doing the roles that she was expected to do, and so she wants to escape from it. The personal experiences the deep ecology and explores the natural environment of the underwater world:

First the air is blue then

it is bluer and then green and then / black I am blacking
out. (34-35)

She feels free and sees the sea as a place where “you breathe differently”. Rich reveals the beauty of nature and the power that it has over living organisms. The protagonist of the poem gets hold of the power coming out of the water, pumping her “blood with power”. There is no boundary in the ocean, and one can feel free and breathe differently. Nature and woman are presented here as one, and that supports and heals each other. She leaves all her social responsibilities and enjoys nature in solitude.

“For the Record” from the second volume is another poem in which Rich shows how nature is innocent about the atrocities committed by humankind, even though the phenomenon of nature may cause natural calamities. Rich discusses the relationship between mankind’s sufferings and his environment, declaring that men and women are responsible for the destruction of themselves. It is their political corruption, neglect, and unjust actions that cause pain and devastation to the people and the world around them. The primary focus of this poem is the environment and the communal devastation that the society is enduring. Rich was one of the many Americans who objected to America’s participation in the Vietnam War. The war had significant environmental implications due to the use of chemical agents to destroy militarily significant vegetation. The vegetation became unable to regenerate, leaving behind bare mudflats for many years. Rich writes:

The clouds and the stars didn’t wage this war
the brooks gave no information
if the mountains spewed stones of fire into the river
it was not taking sides
the raindrop faintly swaying under the leaf
had no political opinions. (1-6)

The clouds, stars, brooks, mountains, and rivers are all victims of the atrocities of the modern-day nuclear weapons used in wars.

Wars cause pollution of the air and water- the elements through which mankind survives. This pollution arising from wars leads to the dislocation of people, and this automatically leads to death due to starvation. This large displacement of people put pressure on the surrounding ecosystems. Forests were cleared in order to provide wood for building shelters and cooking. Rich writes:

The trees didn't volunteer to be cut into boards
nor the thorns for tearing flesh
Look around at all of it. (28-30)

People cut down trees to build homes, not realizing that they should also take the initiative to grow them. Large areas designated as forest land are treeless for this reason. Trees give out oxygen, and due to them, we have rain, and in this way, they help to maintain ecological balance. If we cut trees, the oxygen in the atmosphere will be reduced, affecting the entire ecosystem. Trees breathe the same way as humans. They inhale carbon dioxide and exhale oxygen, while we breathe out carbon dioxide and inhale oxygen. To breathe is to live, and if we take down the trees, we are cut off from the oxygen.

Rich, through these poems, asks her readers to have a holistic view and respect towards our ecology. She has not only made a significant contribution towards inculcation of environmental consciousness but also led the world to believe that no human beings could survive without the ecological system, and it has become the only movement where all the people of the world, irrespective of gender, race, and colour, come together for a genuine purpose.

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